

An Inference Framework for Integrating Mobility Data into Mathematical Epidemic Models

Razvan G. Romanescu^{1,2}

¹Department of Community Health Sciences, University of Manitoba, Canada; 2 – Center for Healthcare Innovation, University of Manitoba, Canada

Abstract

Advances in modeling the spread of infectious diseases have allowed modellers to relax the homogeneous mixing assumption from traditional compartmental models. The recently introduced synthetic network model, which is an SIRS type model based on a non-linear transmission rate, effectively decouples the underlying population network structure from the epidemiological parameters of disease, and has been shown to produce superior fits to multi-wave epidemics. However, inference based on case counts alone generally confounds the effects of the pathogen with those of the contact network, as an increase in either transmissibility or number of connections can lead to large observed counts. An alternate source of data that informs the network alone can therefore improve overall modeling results. Cell phone mobility aggregate data, which report daily numbers of visits to points of interest, provide a proxy for the number of contacts that people establish during their visits. In this paper, we link the transmission rate of the epidemic model with the total number of contacts formed in the population. Inferring the latter from Google Community Mobility Reports data, we develop an integrated epidemic model whose transmission adapts to population mobility. This model is illustrated on the first four waves of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key Words: Infectious disease models, SIRS, epidemics on networks, cell phone mobility

1. Introduction

Mathematical infectious disease models typically produce one curve that describes the trajectory of an epidemic, based on a set of parameters. The model is fit to observed cases of infection, and a best fit curve is produced. This fitted curve is assumed to describe the epidemic in the past and (near) future. In reality, parameters governing transmission change, as individuals adapt to the real or perceived risks of an ongoing epidemic. Public health agencies introduce restrictions on mobility and access, aiming precisely to change relevant transmission parameters and contain the infection. As a result, datasets of observed infection counts are a realization of changing models over time. One solution is to fit piecewise models according to known restrictions. This model building approach amounts to adding parameters and relying on the data to infer the best fitting values for different time segments of the epidemic (Wu et al, 2020; Romanescu et al., 2023). The shortcoming of this approach is that it relies on the same source of data, i.e., case counts, to infer changes in the generating process. This can lead to confounding and identifiability problems, as different changes in the process can produce the same case counts. For example, in a seasonal pathogen, both a less infectious strain, and less social contacts will result in fewer observed cases in the next wave. It would be very desirable to have different types of information that can be used for inference, in addition to case data.

Recently, cell phone mobility data has emerged as a promising source of information to inform the contact network underlying disease transmission. Spatial cell phone locations have been used, at the aggregate level, to identify points of interest where individuals cluster (Chang et al., 2021). Classical

compartmental models would need a more compact representation of the mobility data that can be readily incorporated into an ordinary differential equation (ODE) framework. Google Community Mobility Reports seem to fit the bill, as they provide a single time series of changes in aggregate mobility volume for one location. Although some attempts have been made to model this data, there are currently no best practices on how to use this with epidemiological models.

In this paper, we first review an SIRS epidemiological model based on a non-linear transmission function, in Section 2. We then discuss how the transmission function, which can also be interpreted as the average contact rate of the infectious set, provides a natural link to mobility data, which acts as a proxy to contacts formed in the population. The two sources of data – namely case counts and aggregate mobility, – can then both inform an augmented epidemic model whose transmission rate changes in response to mobility volumes. We fit this model to COVID-19 data from New York in Section 3 to illustrate whether and how including GMR data helps inference. We conclude with a discussion and recommendations for future research and data collection in Section 4.

2. Methods

2.1 Epidemiological Model

The epidemic model we use follows the synthetic network models in Romanescu et al. (2023), which is a discretized ODE-type model of transmission in the susceptible-infected-removed-susceptible (SIRS) setting. The distinguishing features of this framework are that it models daily incidence (y_t) via the effective reproduction number (R_t), instead of modeling total infections (I_t). The advantage of modeling y_t is that it can accommodate a custom generation interval, whereas in the classical ODE formulation, infections decay exponentially. Thus, if w_s is the generation interval, which gives the probability that the time between a primary and secondary infection is s days, then we can express incidence at time $t + 1$ as follows (Abbott et al., 2020; Nishiura & Chowell, 2009):

$$y_{t+1} = R_t \sum_{s=1}^M w_s y_{t+1-s}, \quad (1)$$

where M is the maximum range of the generation interval. Next, R_t can be factored as follows:

$$R_t = \alpha \times S_t \times c_t, \quad (2)$$

where α is the person to person probability of transmission given that a contact exists; S_t is the fraction of all nodes that are still susceptible; and c_t is the average number of contacts of infectious individuals at time t , less one (the primary infector). Recently it has been argued (Romanescu et al., 2023) that $c_t = c(S_t)$, in other words that the contact rate of the changing infectious set decays as a non-linear function of S_t . This assumption requires a well-mixed heterogeneous population, and arises naturally in both network models (with first order degree heterogeneity, see Newman, 2003; Volz, 2008; and others), as well as in randomly mixing populations with heterogeneous susceptibility (as assumed in compartmental ODE models, see Novozhilov, 2008).

The theoretical and practical importance of assuming that R_t is a function of S_t is that we only need to keep track of one unobserved variable, S_t , instead of two variables (S_t and I_t) in the traditional ODE approach. We update S_t as

$$S_{t+1} = S_t - \frac{y_{t+1}}{\rho_t N}, \quad (3)$$

where N is the total population size and ρ_t is the underreporting rate, defined as the fraction of reported cases to actual infections.

We choose the function $c(\cdot)$ to be $c(S_t) = \alpha^{-1} a_1 e^{-a_2(1-S_t)^{a_3}}$, a model adapted from Granich et al. (2009), where a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 are parameters to be estimated from data. This was shown in our previous work to outperform the mass action model (with constant c) by a wide margin in terms of quality of fit to data. Note that α and $c(\cdot)$ are only identifiable as a product and not individually, and

we will use the notation $\tilde{c}(S_t) = \alpha c(S_t)$ when this distinction is important. To be clear, all statistical inference will refer to the function \tilde{c} as opposed to c .

In the SIRS case, the dynamics of transmission on heterogeneous networks is slightly more complicated, but can be approximated as follows. Let S_0 and S_{-1} represent the overall fraction S_t at the beginning of the current epidemic wave, and at the end of the previous wave, respectively. Furthermore, suppose that a fraction ν of infected individuals lose immunity to the current circulating strain of the pathogen at the beginning of a new wave. We use the weighted contact rate in subsequent waves of the epidemic:

$$c_t \left(\frac{S_t}{S_0} \right) = w_A c \left(S_{-1} \times \frac{S_t}{S_0} \right) + w_B c \left(\frac{S_t}{S_0} \right), \quad (4)$$

where $w_A = \frac{S_{-1}(1-\nu)}{S_0}$ and $w_B = \frac{\nu}{S_0}$ and it can be shown that $w_A + w_B = 1$. The effective reproductive number is then computed as $R_t = \alpha S_t c_t(S_t/S_0)$. S_t is updated as in the SIR case. Finally, each wave beyond the first is allowed different person-to-person transmissibility of the strain via parameters ν_2, ν_3, \dots , which give the relative change in transmission compared to α .

2.2 Pre-processing Google Community Mobility Reports data

The Google Community Mobility Reports (GMR) were published between February 2020 and October 2022 and report the change in cell phone traffic volume at different categories of locations, including: work, retail and recreation, parks, public transit, and residential. Changes are reported as percentages compared to a reference baseline defined as the median volume for that day of the week, over a period of 5 weeks between Jan 3–Feb 6, 2020 (Google LLC). Numbers are aggregated to preserve confidentiality, and no absolute values are given.

We pre-process the Community Mobility Reports to account for differences in visits between weekdays and weekends. From the American Time Use Survey we estimate the ratio of time spent on a weekend compared to a weekday in each mobility category (Table 3). A similar approach was taken in Gutierrez-Jara et al. (2022). Choosing weekdays as a single baseline, we express percentage changes for weekends compared to this baseline by multiplying the percent changes in GMR (relative to a Saturday/Sunday during Feb 2020 – March 2020) by the ratio of hours spent in that category during weekends vs. weekdays. For each category apart from residences (R, G, T, P, W), i.e., retail & recreation, grocery & pharmacy, transit stations, parks, workplaces, and homes, we now have a time series of relative changes to the baseline mobility level (i.e., a typical weekday), call it $\mathbf{V}_t = (V_t^R, V_t^G, V_t^T, V_t^P, V_t^W)$, for each day $t = 1, \dots, T$.

2.3 Modeling the reduction in social connectivity as a result of public health orders

2.3.1 Link between total contacts in the population and the contact rate function $c(\cdot)$. In the epidemic model described above, it is possible to recover the total number of contacts in the population from the contact rate function of the infectious set. Assume first a disease that progresses in non-overlapping disease generations, and that infectious individuals recover at the end of one generation. In the SIR framework we can write the total number of contacts of individuals infected in generation g , during time interval $[t_g, t_{g+1})$ as $I_{t_g} \times [c(S_{t_g}) + 1]$, using the definition of $c(\cdot)$. Assuming that everyone is connected to the giant component of the network then a hypothetical disease with $\alpha = 1$ would infect the entire population. Thus, summing up the total contacts of infected individuals across all generations we have:

$$2NE[D] = N \int_0^1 [c(s) + 1] ds, \quad (5)$$

where random variable D is the number of contacts of a random individual in the population. Thus

$$E[D] = 1/2 \int_0^1 [c(s) + 1] ds. \quad (6)$$

Notice that the factor of two comes from the fact that every connection is counted twice under the integral sign: once for the original infector, and once for the infectee. This relationship is important because we can estimate changes in $E[D]$ from other sources (such as mobility data). The absolute value of $E[D]$ may be more difficult to pinpoint because infectious contacts are a subset of social or

mobility contacts. However, since $c(\cdot)$ itself can only be inferred up to a scaling factor, this may not be a problem, as will become evident later.

Figure 1. (Left) Contact rate of the infectious set during an epidemic, as a function of the remaining susceptible fraction. The area of a slice under curve $c(\cdot)$ between S_{t_1} and S_{t_2} gives the average number of contacts (less 1) of typical infected individuals between epidemic ages S_{t_1} and S_{t_2} . (Right) Changes in the original curve $c(\cdot)$ (dashed line) according to the scenario: downscaled (green), tapered (blue), top off (sepia).

As our investigation focuses on changes in contact volumes over time, we need to model ways in which the contact rate $c(\cdot)$ changes on a daily basis. Reducing the contact rate is indeed the goal of public health policy aimed at social restrictions, such as lockdowns and capacity limits. Being able to model these changes is paramount in evaluating the effectiveness of control measures. In Table 1 we imagine a few different scenarios of how this function changes when policies are implemented (denote by $c_q(\cdot)$ the new function under restriction scenario q). Figure 2 graphically illustrates the shift in $c(\cdot)$ for each scenario. While this is by no means an exhaustive list, it does capture a range of possibilities, each having different implications for the total burden of disease, as will be illustrated in the data application.

Scenario 1 is probably the most used in modeling, often by default, and makes no distinction between a drop in transmissibility of the pathogen, and a restriction on individual contacts. Scenario 2 was introduced in our previous work (Romanescu et al, 2023) in the context of network models, and consists of adding an exponential tail to the probability mass function of individual contacts. More exactly, if we let f_1 and f_2 denote the fraction of individuals in the original population with i_1 and i_2 contacts ($i_1 < i_2$), then under restrictions, the new fractions f_1^*, f_2^* satisfy $\frac{f_2^*}{f_1^*} = \varphi^{i_2 - i_1} \frac{f_2}{f_1}$, where $\varphi < 1$ controls the severity of restrictions on the network. This assumption can be shown to imply the tapered scenario in **Table 1**, under a first order network model. This scenario can be argued to be more realistic than a scale reduction, at least in certain situations. Scenario 3 consists of capping average connections at a certain level. This is not necessarily a realistic representation

of past containment efforts, however could be implemented, and we expect would be the most effective among the scenarios considered.

Table 1. Scenarios of reduction in contact rate function.

Scenario	Change relative to $c(\cdot)$	Individual level impact
1. Scaled down	$c_1(S) = Kc(S)$	Individuals “equally” impacted, i.e., everyone loses the same percentage of connections
2. Tapered	$c_2(S) = c(KS)$	Highly connected individuals disproportionately restricted compared to least connected
3. Top off	$c_3(S) = c(\min(S, K))$	Individuals affected tend to have connections above a certain level.

2.4. Joint inference on the epidemic model and mobility data

In what follows, we will let the Mobility Reports inform the restriction level K_t on a daily basis, and use the resulting functions $c_{q,t}(S_t) = c(S_t; K_t; q)$ from Table 1 (where q indexes the scenario) as the daily contact rates when fitting the epidemiologic model. To calibrate K_t we equate the number of total contacts lost (as the difference in area under the curves c and c_q) with the reduction in cell phone traffic at relevant points of interest.

We assume that individuals establish epidemiologically relevant contacts at rates $\mathbf{r} = (r^R, r^G, r^T, r^P, r^W)$ per baseline level of activity in each category, and r^H contact at home. Thus, if contacts were established uniformly and individuals were homogeneous, the average number of contacts formed on day t is $\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H$, where we assume that contacts at home are constant every day. However, similar to the nonlinearity in the epidemiologic model, we may wish to assume that changes in the overall mobility metric affect number of contacts in a non-linear fashion. It seems reasonable to assume that the first 5% of individuals who choose to reduce their mobility in response to a circulating pathogen are behaviorally different from individuals who account for a drop in the metric from 55% to 50% of normal levels. Thus, we compute the mobility metric as $l_{lower} + l_{upper}f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H)$, where f is the standard logistic curve.

We now have two ways to estimate the total number of contacts on a particular day t : one from the GMR data as $\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H$; and a second way via the contact rate function of the SNM, as half the area under the curve $c(s; K_t; q) + 1$. What we wish to do next is to estimate series K_t for assumed reduction scenario q from data in GMR. By equating the two formulations for number of contacts on day t , we have:

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 c(s; K_t; q) ds + \frac{1}{2} = l_{lower} + l_{upper}f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H). \quad (7)$$

We now turn our attention to solving Equation (7) for every reduction scenario in **Table 1**.

2.4.1 Solution for scale down scenario. In this case, $c(S; K_t; 1) = K_t c(S)$ and Equation (7) becomes $K_t/2 \int_0^1 c(s) ds = l_{lower} - 1/2 + l_{upper}f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H)$. Recall from Section 2.2 that $c(s) = \tilde{c}(s)/\alpha$, where \tilde{c} is estimable and α is not. We will therefore express everything in terms of \tilde{c} , and show how α blends in naturally with other unknowns, so that it does not require separate estimation.

We can solve for $K_t = \frac{l_{lower}^* + l_{upper}^* f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H)}{\int_0^1 \tilde{c}(s) ds}$, where $l_{lower}^* = 2\alpha(l_{lower} - \frac{1}{2})$ and $l_{upper}^* = 2\alpha l_{upper}$. With restrictions, model (2) becomes

$$R_{t+1} = S_t \times K_t \times \tilde{c}(S_t) = S_t \times \frac{M_t}{\int_0^1 \tilde{c}(s) ds} \times \tilde{c}(S_t) \quad (8)$$

in the SIR case, where we have denoted $M_t = l_{lower}^* + l_{upper}^* f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H)$. In the SIRS case, Equation (7) does not change, as it is independent of infection or reinfection status. So the middle

term on the RHS of (8) stays the same, however \tilde{c} changes for subsequent waves, according to formula (4). Parameters l_{lower}^* and l_{upper}^* will be chosen as a function of curve \tilde{c} parameters in order to make the scales of the two models for number of contacts comparable, as detailed under ‘Model implementation details’ in the Appendix. The r parameters will be estimated as part of the model fit.

2.4.2 Solution for tapered scenario. In this case, $\int_0^1 c(s; K_t; q) ds = \frac{\int_0^{K_t} \tilde{c}(s) ds}{\alpha K_t}$ (see Appendix for derivation). Thus Equation (7) becomes $\frac{1}{2} \frac{\int_0^{K_t} \tilde{c}(s) ds}{\alpha K_t} + \frac{1}{2} = l_{lower} + l_{upper} f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H)$, which simplifies to $\frac{\int_0^{K_t} \tilde{c}(s) ds}{K_t} = l_{lower}^* + l_{upper}^* f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H) = M_t$, for the same definitions as above. The resulting integral equation

$$\int_0^{K_t} \tilde{c}(s) ds = K_t M_t \quad (9)$$

needs to be solved for K_t , on each day t , which gives the amount of restriction in the contact rate of individuals consistent with the observed mobility for that day. Denoting K_t^* the solution of (10), the restricted epidemiologic model becomes $R_t = S_t \times \tilde{c}(K_t^* S_t)$.

2.4.3 Solution for top off scenario. Here, K_t is the level of the susceptible fraction from which the contact rate tops off. Equation (7) leads to

$$\int_0^{K_t} \tilde{c}(s) ds + (1 - K_t) \tilde{c}(K_t) = l_{lower}^* + l_{upper}^* f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H) = M_t \quad (10)$$

for the same definitions of l_{lower}^* and l_{upper}^* . Solving (11) numerically for K_t , the restricted \mathcal{R}_e becomes $R_t = S_t \times \tilde{c}(\min(K_t^*, S_t))$.

3. Results

We illustrate this framework on the time series of COVID-19 cases from New York State, over the period March 2020 – February 2022, which is comprised of four visible waves. The exact definition of waves is described elsewhere (Romanescu et al., 2023). Data obtained from Google Community Mobility Reports for the corresponding period is preprocessed as described in Methods. Other epidemiological parameters are taken from Romanescu et al. (2023) and references therein. We further consider an offset vector giving the delay for each day, between GMR and COVID reported cases, which is computed as: $delay_t = incubation_t + case_delay - GMR_delay$. Here, incubation periods are specific to each strain (Wu et al., 2022): for wildtype 6.65 days, for alpha variant 5.00 days, for delta 4.41 and for omicron 3.42 days. Reporting delay of COVID cases is estimated to be 3.3 days, while mobility data is assumed to have a delay of 2 days (Aktay et al., 2020). To simplify analysis, we only include the categories ‘Workplace’ and ‘Retail and Recreation’, assuming that other activities are less important for epidemiologic contacts (i.e., $r^G = r^T = r^P = 0$).

We first fit the assumed curve $c(\cdot)$ without any restrictions to the entire dataset. We then fit both the curve model and mass action models including the GMR data, under scenarios 1 and 2. Note that the mass action model can only accommodate the scaled-down scenario. Finally, based on previous results, we allow for a single drop in mobility index M_t during the times of public health restrictions, in order to accommodate for any extra effects not captured by the Google data. This will be given by parameter β_0 such that $M_t = l_{lower}^* + l_{upper}^* f(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H - \beta_0 I_{restrictions})$. Thus, the β_0 shift is applied during the time that public health restrictions were in place (2020-Mar-22 to 2021-Jun-14), accounting for a delay of $incubation_t + case_delay$. Figure 1 a) and b) shows the fitted curves, and parameter estimates are given in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Parameter estimates of the fits and negative log likelihood values for each assumed reduction scenario.

Parameters		No reduction	Scaled down	Tapered	Scaled down (incl. β_0)	Tapered (incl. β_0)
$\tilde{c}(S_t)$	a_1	100 (-)	20 (-)	12.67 (5.98)	3.20 (0.13)	5.38 (-)
	a_2	4.82 (0.055)	2.47 (0.092)	2.65 (0.46)	300 (-)	2.25 (-)
	a_3	0.022 (0.002)	0.030 (0.004)	0.145 (0.038)	4.68 (0.08)	0.279 (-)
loss of immunity rate ν		0.015 (0.004)	0.078 (0.029)	0.57 (0.26)	0.42 (0.02)	1.00 (-)
relative variant transmissibility for waves 2+ ($\nu_1 = 1$)	ν_2	1.12 (0.03)	0.88 (0.03)	0.79 (0.02)	1.13 (0.04)	1.26 (0.01)
	ν_3	1.40 (0.06)	0.94 (0.05)	0.72 (0.08)	0.50 (0.01)	0.44 (0.01)
	ν_4	1.84 (0.09)	1.32 (0.09)	0.94 (0.11)	0.74 (0.02)	0.70 (-)
activity contact rates (r)	r^{Home}	-	-3.0 (-)	-3.0 (0.019)	-3.0 (-)	1.68 (-)
	r^{Retail}	-	0.50 (0.07)	1.46 (0.017)	0.26 (0.043)	0.64 (-)
	r^{Work}	-	0.71 (0.13)	1.74 (0.042)	0.36 (0.081)	-0.29 (-)
	β_0	-	-	-	0.96 (0.056)	2.99 (-)
Variance parameter (u)		8439.55 (678.39)	6338.22 (505.50)	7082.80 (549.25)	2363.27 (176.83)	2275.09 (167.61)
$-l(\theta)$		4119.4	4092.6	4090.6	3906.4	3905.0
# of parameters		8	10	10	11	11
AIC		8254.8	8205.2	8201.2	7834.8	7832

Notice from the likelihood and AIC values in **Table 2** that including the GMR data leads to a significant improvement in fit. However, adding the β_0 shift leads to an even larger quantitative and qualitative improvement in fit. Looking at the values of restriction level K_t in the downscaled scenario, we notice that even though the Google data shows generally lower activity during public health restrictions, it is not nearly as pronounced as the drop implied from case data (**Figure 4** in the Appendix). The change in level K_t under the tapered scenario is qualitatively similar (results not shown). Even though the parallel drop we introduce in K_t is somewhat arbitrary, it does suggest that the mobility metric may not be sensitive enough to capture the loss of contacts relevant to disease spread. An explanation might be that the categories defined by Google are too broad, and blend contacts with high and low risk to disease spread. For instance, the Retail and Recreation category includes bars and restaurants, where individuals stay in close contact for extended periods and engage in casual conversation, as well as large retail stores (e.g., Walmart), which typically do not offer the same opportunity to transmit infection. Public health orders specifically targeted venues in the former category with closures, while allowing those in the latter to stay open (for good reason). It is entirely conceivable that individuals changed their behavior in response to such restrictions by going shopping more instead of going to restaurants. This change is likely to significantly impact case numbers, however may not have much effect on the GMS, which counts both types of venues the same.

Figure 2. Fit of the curve model to the NY data under different reduction scenarios: (upper) no reduction (black), downscaled (blue), tapered (gold). (Lower) downscaled (blue), and tapered scenarios (gold), allowing for an extra parameter in M_t .

In terms of what distinguishes the different reduction scenarios for curve c, it would seem from Figure 2 that the fits are similar, and this is true because models are overparameterized, and the excess degrees of freedom can make different models fit the data closely. However, to see the difference between scenarios, we need to keep M_t fixed, i.e., use the same overall daily loss of contacts, and solve for the corresponding levels K_t under each scenario separately. Then we compute and compare the curves starting from the same epidemiological parameters, but using the K_t time series that was calculated under each scenario. We do this in Figure 3, where the starting point is the parameter set in Table 2 for the tapered scenario including β_0 . As we can see, the implied curves are significantly different: the shift in c under the downscaled scenario is relatively ineffective at curbing spread, and the top off scenario is most effective. The total burden of disease in terms of infections during the four waves considered is 17,937,421 infections in the downscaled, 10,102,390 in the tapered, and 5,208,708 in the top off scenario. The explanation likely has to do with the shape of the curve c, and how the same reduction in area under the curve can have a widely different impact on epidemic dynamics depending on scenario.

Figure 3. Daily implied infections under the three scenarios, matched for daily contact volumes: downscaled (blue), tapered (gold), top off (red).

3. Discussion

This paper presented a framework for integrating aggregate cell phone mobility data into a model of infectious disease spread. It also demonstrated how different scenarios for reduction in average number of connections could have a profound impact on reducing the total burden of disease. The potential of this research is quite enticing; for instance, it allows public health practitioners to answer questions such as “if we were to mandate working from home for two days a week, what would the impact be on spread?” With a well-calibrated model, this can be predicted by simply plugging in $V_{t,new}^W = 3/5 V_t^W$ into the model and noting the difference in trajectory. As well, being able to estimate how the contact rate curve changes in response to policy can be invaluable in designing future interventions.

The availability of cell phone data, which can inform contacts between individuals, is welcome in infectious disease modeling; however there is room for growth in both the quality of this data and in how it is modeled. Starting with the data itself, the Google Community Mobility Reports were introduced as another one of the Google suite of products, such as Google Maps with the general aim of providing “insights into changes in mobility patterns” (Aktay et al., 2020). There is no indication that this was intended to be used by epidemiologists, so we can assume that infectious disease modeling was not the intended application. However, a mobility metric based on cell phone data is certainly a much needed tool for modellers, as this paper and others (Chang, 2021) have shown. A couple of recommendations for any future iterations of GMR to make them more useful as research tools are as follows: 1) keep a single baseline, as opposed to changing the baseline according to the day of the week. Not having explicit baseline for each day introduces unnecessary variability in the dataset (in the present paper, we made the assumption that all weekdays are alike, as Saturday and Sunday). 2) refine the categories to be more useful to infection spread; in particular,

points of interest that were specifically targeted by public health orders, such as dining and entertainment venues, etc. should be reported separately from other retail and recreation categories. In addition to improving the quality of input data, future efforts will need to focus on how to model and interpret mobility data. Unless working with very granular spatial data, which requires large, intractable models, aggregate mobility data will necessarily collapse different behavioural patterns into single numbers. As a result, having insight into such patterns, at the individual and population level will be necessary to make the best use of the data. For example, there are two noticeable patterns in the implied restriction level K_t in **Figure 4**: 1) a general drop compared to pre-pandemic levels of more than 20%, from which the population does not recover; and 2) three lows corresponding roughly to the three largest COVID-19 waves. There are a couple of insights here: first, that there is likely a risk-averse segment of the population whose activity does not bounce back, even after official restrictions are lifted. Second, given that the data strongly favors a large reduction in K_t during the mandated orders, as shown by the fits including β_0 , we would speculate that these three visible dips had a greater impact than can be captured on a linear or logistic scale. Perhaps that these two hypothesized segments of the population – one that stays home no matter what, and the other that stays home only when the risk is high, or when forced to –, should be modeled separately. In any case, more research is needed to understand how individual compliance or risk aversion can be used to inform infectious disease models.

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Appendix

Model implementation details. For scenarios 1 and 3 we set $l_{lower}^* = \tilde{c}(0)$ and $l_{lower}^* = 0$ for scenario 2. For all three scenarios, we set $l_{upper}^* = [\int_0^1 \tilde{c}(s)ds - l_{lower}^*] / f(\max(\mathbf{V}_t \cdot \mathbf{r} + r^H))$, where the maximum is taken over t . This guarantees that Equations (8 – 10) have solutions for each day t . As well, this particular choice implies that the maximum of M_t corresponds to no restrictions ($K_t = 1$), which is meaningful for the dataset considered, which also covers a time period before the pandemic. If fitting a time period that falls entirely under restrictions, the denominator in l_{upper}^* can simply be set to 1.

Equations (9) and (10) are solved numerically for K_t using *uniroot* solver in R. The lower incomplete gamma function used in the integral for functions \tilde{c} is computed via R function *gammainc*. Optimization of model parameters is done by maximizing the log-likelihood via *optim* function in R, using gradient descent. The likelihood function is based on the model for infections $y_t / \rho_t \sim N(f_t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) / \rho_t, u f_t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) / \rho_t)$, where f_t denotes the epidemic curve model on day t . The fits shown in the main text correspond to the MLE $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. Due to the relatively large number of parameter, optimization might present different areas of the parameter space with comparably good fit. As a general strategy, we start the optimizer from the best fits in Romanescu et al. (2023) and may place interval restrictions on the parameters common with that model in order to preserve those fits qualitatively. In this way, the optimizer focuses on searching for the best $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ parameters (new to this model) that are consistent with those fits. As a disclaimer, due to the large parameter space and inherent identifiability problems with this class of models, results shown may prove to be local as opposed to global maxima of the likelihood function in a wider search.

Solving Equation (7) in the tapered case. Under restrictions, assume $c^*(x) = c(\psi x)$, where ψ is the severity of contacts, and also that D^* is the number of contacts of a random individual. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2E[D^*] &= \int_0^1 c^*(x) + 1 dx = 1 + \int_0^1 c(\psi x) dx \\
 &= 1 + \int \frac{c(y)}{\psi} dy = 1 + \frac{1}{\psi} \int_{y/\psi=0}^{y/\psi=1} c \Big|_{y/\psi=0}^{y/\psi=1} \\
 &= 1 + \frac{1}{\psi} \left[\int c(\psi) - \int c(0) \right] \\
 &= 1 + \frac{\int c(\psi) - \int c(0)}{\psi},
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\int c(x)$ is the antiderivative of c , evaluated at x . In practice, we only know $\tilde{c}(x) = \alpha c(x) \Rightarrow E[D^*] = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\int \tilde{c}(\psi) - \int \tilde{c}(0)}{2\alpha\psi}$. Note further that for $\tilde{c}(S_t) = a_1 e^{-a_2(1-S_t)^{a_3}}$ as used in the text, we have $\int_0^x \tilde{c}(s) ds = \frac{a_1 \{-\gamma(\frac{1}{a_3}, a_2(1-x)^{a_3}) + \gamma(\frac{1}{a_3}, a_2)\}}{a_3 a_2^{1/a_3}}$, where $\gamma(x, a)$ is the lower incomplete gamma function.

Table 3. Average hours per day spent in activities related to the GMR categories, from the American Time Use Survey.

Activity category	Average hours per day, civilian population		Ratio of averages, weekend/weekday
	Weekdays	Weekends and holidays	
Retail & Recreation	0.98	1.86	1.898
Grocery	0.09	0.13	1.444
Work	4.63	1.26	0.272
Travel (overall)	1.2	1.11	0.925

Figure 4. Restriction level K_t implied by the fitted model under the downscaled scenario: (upper) excluding β_0 in the fit; (lower) including β_0 .